

Tableau des distances génétiques interpécifiques

Gruhn et al. : Le genre Resinicium dans les Outre-Mer, avec la description de sept espèces nouvelles

Taxon cible	Taxon correspondant	% moyen	% minimum	% maximum
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium bicolor	0.1889	0.1882	0.1895
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium confertum	0.1810	0.1804	0.1816
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium friabile	0.1839	0.1702	0.1946
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium luteolus	0.1391	0.1238	0.1500
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1648	0.1605	0.1690
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1771	0.1766	0.1777
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium monticola	0.0874	0.0860	0.0888
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium mutabile	0.1396	0.1356	0.1422
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1363	0.1358	0.1368
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1756	0.1750	0.1762
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1732	0.1584	0.2277
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium tenue	0.1843	0.1826	0.1859
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium yunnanense	0.1917	0.1912	0.1922
Resinicium austroasianum	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2729	0.2654	0.2766
Resinicium austroasianum	Rickenella fibula	0.1866	0.1850	0.1882
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium simile	0.1271	0.1267	0.1276
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1453	0.1399	0.1487
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1327	0.1307	0.1347
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium guttatum	0.1327	0.1307	0.1347
Resinicium austroasianum	Resinicium mahoreense	0.1651	0.1619	0.1682
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1889	0.1882	0.1895
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium confertum	0.0429	0.0429	0.0429
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium friabile	0.0449	0.0374	0.0487
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium luteolus	0.1734	0.1672	0.1820
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1897	0.1822	0.2005
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.0456	0.0456	0.0456
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium monticola	0.1471	0.1460	0.1481
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium mutabile	0.1817	0.1797	0.1836
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1762	0.1762	0.1762
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium rimulosum	0.0392	0.0386	0.0398
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium saccharicola	0.0524	0.0433	0.0685
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium tenue	0.0386	0.0386	0.0386
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium yunnanense	0.0767	0.0728	0.0806
Resinicium bicolor	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2416	0.2270	0.2577
Resinicium bicolor	Rickenella fibula	0.2050	0.2050	0.2050
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium simile	0.1705	0.1705	0.1705
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1678	0.1526	0.1785
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1595	0.1595	0.1595
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium guttatum	0.1824	0.1824	0.1824
Resinicium bicolor	Resinicium mahoreense	0.1778	0.1778	0.1778
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1810	0.1804	0.1816
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium bicolor	0.0429	0.0429	0.0429
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium friabile	0.0369	0.0302	0.0429
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium luteolus	0.1619	0.1584	0.1700
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1743	0.1667	0.1801
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.0160	0.0160	0.0160
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium monticola	0.1524	0.1513	0.1534
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium mutabile	0.1778	0.1732	0.1804
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1707	0.1707	0.1707
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium rimulosum	0.0375	0.0348	0.0402
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium saccharicola	0.0559	0.0457	0.0776

Resinicium confertum	Resinicium tenue	0.0307	0.0307	0.0307
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium yunnanense	0.0669	0.0629	0.0708
Resinicium confertum	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2409	0.2289	0.2522
Resinicium confertum	Rickenella fibula	0.2004	0.2004	0.2004
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium simile	0.1635	0.1635	0.1635
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1593	0.1456	0.1692
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1443	0.1443	0.1443
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium guttatum	0.1746	0.1746	0.1746
Resinicium confertum	Resinicium mahorense	0.1652	0.1652	0.1652
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1839	0.1702	0.1946
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium bicolor	0.0449	0.0374	0.0487
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium confertum	0.0369	0.0302	0.0429
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium luteolus	0.1581	0.1308	0.1736
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1851	0.1639	0.1996
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.0351	0.0240	0.0433
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium monticola	0.1524	0.1393	0.1645
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium mutabile	0.1748	0.1624	0.1911
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1675	0.1565	0.1791
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium rimulosum	0.0335	0.0258	0.0440
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium saccharicola	0.0462	0.0269	0.0676
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium tenue	0.0348	0.0299	0.0406
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium yunnanense	0.0348	0.0086	0.0536
Resinicium friabile	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2366	0.2116	0.2624
Resinicium friabile	Rickenella fibula	0.2026	0.1919	0.2148
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium simile	0.1665	0.1562	0.1778
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1528	0.1258	0.1705
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1481	0.1392	0.1572
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium guttatum	0.1713	0.1571	0.1820
Resinicium friabile	Resinicium mahorense	0.1733	0.1649	0.1885
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1391	0.1238	0.1500
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium bicolor	0.1734	0.1672	0.1820
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium confertum	0.1619	0.1584	0.1700
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium friabile	0.1581	0.1308	0.1736
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1467	0.1246	0.1592
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1695	0.1588	0.1784
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium monticola	0.1077	0.1010	0.1160
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium mutabile	0.1017	0.0948	0.1079
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium nouraguense	0.0906	0.0842	0.0945
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1610	0.1475	0.1773
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1600	0.1274	0.2085
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium tenue	0.1695	0.1634	0.1776
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium yunnanense	0.1756	0.1569	0.1987
Resinicium luteolus	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2443	0.2112	0.2823
Resinicium luteolus	Rickenella fibula	0.1898	0.1837	0.1946
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium simile	0.0779	0.0690	0.0882
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.0311	0.0157	0.0376
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium borbonicum	0.0845	0.0796	0.0885
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium guttatum	0.0977	0.0871	0.1023
Resinicium luteolus	Resinicium mahorense	0.1360	0.1196	0.1449
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1648	0.1605	0.1690
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium bicolor	0.1897	0.1822	0.2005
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium confertum	0.1743	0.1667	0.1801
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium friabile	0.1851	0.1639	0.1996
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium luteolus	0.1467	0.1246	0.1592
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1886	0.1837	0.1930

Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium monticola	0.1405	0.1322	0.1506
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium mutabile	0.1473	0.1375	0.1583
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1336	0.1256	0.1429
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1812	0.1701	0.1900
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1814	0.1601	0.2288
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium tenue	0.1839	0.1760	0.1910
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium yunnanense	0.2105	0.1929	0.2232
Resinicium grandisporum	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2507	0.2266	0.2818
Resinicium grandisporum	Rickenella fibula	0.1856	0.1745	0.1971
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium simile	0.1612	0.1547	0.1685
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1469	0.1223	0.1633
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1450	0.1354	0.1529
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium guttatum	0.1639	0.1606	0.1675
Resinicium grandisporum	Resinicium mahorensense	0.0574	0.0510	0.0706
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1771	0.1766	0.1777
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium bicolor	0.0456	0.0456	0.0456
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium confertum	0.0160	0.0160	0.0160
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium friabile	0.0351	0.0240	0.0433
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium luteolus	0.1695	0.1588	0.1784
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1886	0.1837	0.1930
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium monticola	0.1651	0.1640	0.1663
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium mutabile	0.1845	0.1835	0.1862
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1745	0.1745	0.1745
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium rimulosum	0.0434	0.0411	0.0457
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium saccharicola	0.0506	0.0433	0.0717
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium tenue	0.0205	0.0205	0.0205
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium yunnanense	0.0323	0.0323	0.0323
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2550	0.2506	0.2598
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Rickenella fibula	0.2241	0.2241	0.2241
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium simile	0.1777	0.1777	0.1777
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1693	0.1520	0.1751
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1632	0.1632	0.1632
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium guttatum	0.1770	0.1770	0.1770
Resinicium lateastrocystidium	Resinicium mahorensense	0.1758	0.1758	0.1758
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium austroasianum	0.0874	0.0860	0.0888
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium bicolor	0.1471	0.1460	0.1481
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium confertum	0.1524	0.1513	0.1534
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium friabile	0.1524	0.1393	0.1645
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium luteolus	0.1077	0.1010	0.1160
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1405	0.1322	0.1506
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1651	0.1640	0.1663
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium mutabile	0.1098	0.1000	0.1167
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1022	0.1011	0.1033
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1404	0.1362	0.1447
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1436	0.1299	0.1734
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium tenue	0.1531	0.1521	0.1542
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium yunnanense	0.1830	0.1784	0.1876
Resinicium monticola	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2381	0.2265	0.2484
Resinicium monticola	Rickenella fibula	0.1681	0.1670	0.1691
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium simile	0.0965	0.0954	0.0975
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1082	0.0978	0.1159
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium borbonicum	0.0969	0.0959	0.0980
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium guttatum	0.1180	0.1169	0.1191
Resinicium monticola	Resinicium mahorensense	0.1408	0.1397	0.1419
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1396	0.1356	0.1422

Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium bicolor	0.1817	0.1797	0.1836
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium confertum	0.1778	0.1732	0.1804
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium friabile	0.1748	0.1624	0.1911
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium luteolus	0.1017	0.0948	0.1079
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1473	0.1375	0.1583
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1845	0.1835	0.1862
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium monticola	0.1098	0.1000	0.1167
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium nouraguense	0.0403	0.0398	0.0420
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1784	0.1680	0.1858
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1683	0.1561	0.1839
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium tenue	0.1774	0.1755	0.1792
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium yunnanense	0.2087	0.1975	0.2188
Resinicium mutabile	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2638	0.2418	0.2967
Resinicium mutabile	Rickenella fibula	0.1796	0.1674	0.1855
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium simile	0.1019	0.0962	0.1043
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.0974	0.0788	0.1103
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium borbonicum	0.0997	0.0926	0.1024
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium guttatum	0.1213	0.1179	0.1224
Resinicium mutabile	Resinicium mahoreense	0.1329	0.1230	0.1387
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1363	0.1358	0.1368
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium bicolor	0.1762	0.1762	0.1762
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium confertum	0.1707	0.1707	0.1707
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium friabile	0.1675	0.1565	0.1791
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium luteolus	0.0906	0.0842	0.0945
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1336	0.1256	0.1429
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1745	0.1745	0.1745
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium monticola	0.1022	0.1011	0.1033
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium mutabile	0.0403	0.0398	0.0420
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1707	0.1656	0.1758
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1642	0.1550	0.1704
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium tenue	0.1740	0.1740	0.1740
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium yunnanense	0.2025	0.1986	0.2063
Resinicium nouraguense	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2578	0.2461	0.2812
Resinicium nouraguense	Rickenella fibula	0.1818	0.1818	0.1818
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium simile	0.1016	0.1016	0.1016
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.0835	0.0760	0.0890
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium borbonicum	0.0865	0.0865	0.0865
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium guttatum	0.1028	0.1028	0.1028
Resinicium nouraguense	Resinicium mahoreense	0.1286	0.1286	0.1286
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1756	0.1750	0.1762
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium bicolor	0.0392	0.0386	0.0398
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium confertum	0.0375	0.0348	0.0402
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium friabile	0.0335	0.0258	0.0440
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium luteolus	0.1610	0.1475	0.1773
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1812	0.1701	0.1900
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.0434	0.0411	0.0457
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium monticola	0.1404	0.1362	0.1447
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium mutabile	0.1784	0.1680	0.1858
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1707	0.1656	0.1758
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium saccharicola	0.0460	0.0351	0.0605
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium tenue	0.0331	0.0305	0.0357
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium yunnanense	0.0592	0.0551	0.0663
Resinicium rimulosum	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2412	0.2254	0.2534
Resinicium rimulosum	Rickenella fibula	0.1981	0.1950	0.2013
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium simile	0.1609	0.1604	0.1614

Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1562	0.1362	0.1681
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1437	0.1393	0.1480
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium guttatum	0.1749	0.1738	0.1761
Resinicium rimulosum	Resinicium mahorense	0.1659	0.1648	0.1670
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1732	0.1584	0.2277
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium bicolor	0.0524	0.0433	0.0685
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium confertum	0.0559	0.0457	0.0776
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium friabile	0.0462	0.0269	0.0676
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium luteolus	0.1600	0.1274	0.2085
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1814	0.1601	0.2288
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.0506	0.0433	0.0717
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium monticola	0.1436	0.1299	0.1734
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium mutabile	0.1683	0.1561	0.1839
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1642	0.1550	0.1704
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium rimulosum	0.0460	0.0351	0.0605
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium tenue	0.0483	0.0413	0.0616
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium yunnanense	0.0702	0.0463	0.0919
Resinicium saccharicola	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2536	0.2319	0.3110
Resinicium saccharicola	Rickenella fibula	0.2021	0.1915	0.2154
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium simile	0.1606	0.1477	0.1855
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1556	0.1229	0.1739
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1472	0.1372	0.1613
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium guttatum	0.1647	0.1500	0.1947
Resinicium saccharicola	Resinicium mahorense	0.1656	0.1576	0.1775
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1843	0.1826	0.1859
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium bicolor	0.0386	0.0386	0.0386
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium confertum	0.0307	0.0307	0.0307
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium friabile	0.0348	0.0299	0.0406
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium luteolus	0.1695	0.1634	0.1776
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1839	0.1760	0.1910
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.0205	0.0205	0.0205
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium monticola	0.1531	0.1521	0.1542
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium mutabile	0.1774	0.1755	0.1792
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1740	0.1740	0.1740
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium rimulosum	0.0331	0.0305	0.0357
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium saccharicola	0.0483	0.0413	0.0616
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium yunnanense	0.0642	0.0603	0.0682
Resinicium tenue	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2373	0.2229	0.2533
Resinicium tenue	Rickenella fibula	0.2029	0.2029	0.2029
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium simile	0.1726	0.1726	0.1726
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1603	0.1413	0.1720
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1534	0.1534	0.1534
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium guttatum	0.1824	0.1824	0.1824
Resinicium tenue	Resinicium mahorense	0.1689	0.1689	0.1689
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1917	0.1912	0.1922
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium bicolor	0.0767	0.0728	0.0806
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium confertum	0.0669	0.0629	0.0708
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium friabile	0.0348	0.0086	0.0536
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium luteolus	0.1756	0.1569	0.1987
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium grandisporum	0.2105	0.1929	0.2232
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.0323	0.0323	0.0323
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium monticola	0.1830	0.1784	0.1876
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium mutabile	0.2087	0.1975	0.2188
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium nouraguense	0.2025	0.1986	0.2063
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium rimulosum	0.0592	0.0551	0.0663

Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium saccharicola	0.0702	0.0463	0.0919
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium tenue	0.0642	0.0603	0.0682
Resinicium yunnanense	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2586	0.2479	0.2703
Resinicium yunnanense	Rickenella fibula	0.2302	0.2267	0.2337
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium simile	0.1845	0.1824	0.1866
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1673	0.1386	0.1875
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1793	0.1757	0.1830
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium guttatum	0.1795	0.1795	0.1795
Resinicium yunnanense	Resinicium mahorense	0.1771	0.1771	0.1771
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium austroasianum	0.2729	0.2654	0.2766
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium bicolor	0.2416	0.2270	0.2577
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium confertum	0.2409	0.2289	0.2522
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium friabile	0.2366	0.2116	0.2624
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium luteolus	0.2443	0.2112	0.2823
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium grandisporum	0.2507	0.2266	0.2818
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.2550	0.2506	0.2598
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium monticola	0.2381	0.2265	0.2484
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium mutabile	0.2638	0.2418	0.2967
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium nouraguense	0.2578	0.2461	0.2812
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium rimulosum	0.2412	0.2254	0.2534
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium saccharicola	0.2536	0.2319	0.3110
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium tenue	0.2373	0.2229	0.2533
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium yunnanense	0.2586	0.2479	0.2703
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Rickenella fibula	0.2182	0.1962	0.2561
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium simile	0.2490	0.2322	0.2711
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.2271	0.1951	0.2539
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium borbonicum	0.2423	0.2238	0.2687
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium guttatum	0.2489	0.2376	0.2716
Skvortzovia furfuracea	Resinicium mahorense	0.2419	0.2227	0.2664
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1866	0.1850	0.1882
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium bicolor	0.2050	0.2050	0.2050
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium confertum	0.2004	0.2004	0.2004
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium friabile	0.2026	0.1919	0.2148
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium luteolus	0.1898	0.1837	0.1946
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1856	0.1745	0.1971
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.2241	0.2241	0.2241
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium monticola	0.1681	0.1670	0.1691
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium mutabile	0.1796	0.1674	0.1855
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1818	0.1818	0.1818
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1981	0.1950	0.2013
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium saccharicola	0.2021	0.1915	0.2154
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium tenue	0.2029	0.2029	0.2029
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium yunnanense	0.2302	0.2267	0.2337
Rickenella fibula	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2182	0.1962	0.2561
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium simile	0.1842	0.1842	0.1842
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1776	0.1593	0.1898
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1824	0.1824	0.1824
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium guttatum	0.1991	0.1991	0.1991
Rickenella fibula	Resinicium mahorense	0.1837	0.1837	0.1837
Resinicium simile	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1271	0.1267	0.1276
Resinicium simile	Resinicium bicolor	0.1705	0.1705	0.1705
Resinicium simile	Resinicium confertum	0.1635	0.1635	0.1635
Resinicium simile	Resinicium friabile	0.1665	0.1562	0.1778
Resinicium simile	Resinicium luteolus	0.0779	0.0690	0.0882
Resinicium simile	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1612	0.1547	0.1685

Resinicium simile	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1777	0.1777	0.1777
Resinicium simile	Resinicium monticola	0.0965	0.0954	0.0975
Resinicium simile	Resinicium mutabile	0.1019	0.0962	0.1043
Resinicium simile	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1016	0.1016	0.1016
Resinicium simile	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1609	0.1604	0.1614
Resinicium simile	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1606	0.1477	0.1855
Resinicium simile	Resinicium tenue	0.1726	0.1726	0.1726
Resinicium simile	Resinicium yunnanense	0.1845	0.1824	0.1866
Resinicium simile	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2490	0.2322	0.2711
Resinicium simile	Rickenella fibula	0.1842	0.1842	0.1842
Resinicium simile	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.0899	0.0870	0.0923
Resinicium simile	Resinicium borbonicum	0.0649	0.0649	0.0649
Resinicium simile	Resinicium guttatum	0.0449	0.0449	0.0449
Resinicium simile	Resinicium mahorensense	0.1486	0.1486	0.1486
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1453	0.1399	0.1487
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium bicolor	0.1678	0.1526	0.1785
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium confertum	0.1593	0.1456	0.1692
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium friabile	0.1528	0.1258	0.1705
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium luteolus	0.0311	0.0157	0.0376
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1469	0.1223	0.1633
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1693	0.1520	0.1751
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium monticola	0.1082	0.0978	0.1159
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium mutabile	0.0974	0.0788	0.1103
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium nouraguense	0.0835	0.0760	0.0890
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1562	0.1362	0.1681
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1556	0.1229	0.1739
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium tenue	0.1603	0.1413	0.1720
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium yunnanense	0.1673	0.1386	0.1875
Resinicium gastrodiae	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2271	0.1951	0.2539
Resinicium gastrodiae	Rickenella fibula	0.1776	0.1593	0.1898
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium simile	0.0899	0.0870	0.0923
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium borbonicum	0.0749	0.0716	0.0815
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium guttatum	0.0859	0.0856	0.0867
Resinicium gastrodiae	Resinicium mahorensense	0.1238	0.1019	0.1311
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1327	0.1307	0.1347
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium bicolor	0.1595	0.1595	0.1595
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium confertum	0.1443	0.1443	0.1443
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium friabile	0.1481	0.1392	0.1572
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium luteolus	0.0845	0.0796	0.0885
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1450	0.1354	0.1529
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1632	0.1632	0.1632
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium monticola	0.0969	0.0959	0.0980
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium mutabile	0.0997	0.0926	0.1024
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium nouraguense	0.0865	0.0865	0.0865
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1437	0.1393	0.1480
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1472	0.1372	0.1613
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium tenue	0.1534	0.1534	0.1534
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium yunnanense	0.1793	0.1757	0.1830
Resinicium borbonicum	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2423	0.2238	0.2687
Resinicium borbonicum	Rickenella fibula	0.1824	0.1824	0.1824
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium simile	0.0649	0.0649	0.0649
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.0749	0.0716	0.0815
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium guttatum	0.0494	0.0494	0.0494
Resinicium borbonicum	Resinicium mahorensense	0.1330	0.1330	0.1330
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1327	0.1307	0.1347

Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium bicolor	0.1824	0.1824	0.1824
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium confertum	0.1746	0.1746	0.1746
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium friabile	0.1713	0.1571	0.1820
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium luteolus	0.0977	0.0871	0.1023
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium grandisporum	0.1639	0.1606	0.1675
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1770	0.1770	0.1770
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium monticola	0.1180	0.1169	0.1191
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium mutabile	0.1213	0.1179	0.1224
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1028	0.1028	0.1028
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1749	0.1738	0.1761
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1647	0.1500	0.1947
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium tenue	0.1824	0.1824	0.1824
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium yunnanense	0.1795	0.1795	0.1795
Resinicium guttatum	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2489	0.2376	0.2716
Resinicium guttatum	Rickenella fibula	0.1991	0.1991	0.1991
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium simile	0.0449	0.0449	0.0449
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.0859	0.0856	0.0867
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium borbonicum	0.0494	0.0494	0.0494
Resinicium guttatum	Resinicium mahorense	0.1562	0.1562	0.1562
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium austroasianum	0.1651	0.1619	0.1682
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium bicolor	0.1778	0.1778	0.1778
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium confertum	0.1652	0.1652	0.1652
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium friabile	0.1733	0.1649	0.1885
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium luteolus	0.1360	0.1196	0.1449
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium grandisporum	0.0574	0.0510	0.0706
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium lateastrocystidium	0.1758	0.1758	0.1758
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium monticola	0.1408	0.1397	0.1419
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium mutabile	0.1329	0.1230	0.1387
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium nouraguense	0.1286	0.1286	0.1286
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium rimulosum	0.1659	0.1648	0.1670
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium saccharicola	0.1656	0.1576	0.1775
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium tenue	0.1689	0.1689	0.1689
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium yunnanense	0.1771	0.1771	0.1771
Resinicium mahorense	Skvortzovia furfuracea	0.2419	0.2227	0.2664
Resinicium mahorense	Rickenella fibula	0.1837	0.1837	0.1837
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium simile	0.1486	0.1486	0.1486
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium gastrodiae	0.1238	0.1019	0.1311
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium borbonicum	0.1330	0.1330	0.1330
Resinicium mahorense	Resinicium guttatum	0.1562	0.1562	0.1562

